

Women's work in the
Early Dynastic Period

Mastaba S3038:
a new perspective on
old data

Female *ka*-servant
in the Old Kingdom

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Detail of the limestone stela (1/AS104/2018) belonging to the scribe of the treasury and royal *wab*-priest Sekhemka and his spouse, king's acquaintance Henutsen, found in the eastern wall of the tomb of Nyankhseshat (AS 104) (photo P. Košárek)

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Some notes on the female *ka*-servant in the Old Kingdom

Raúl Sánchez Casado¹

ABSTRACT

The iconographic repertoire of the Old Kingdom tombs seems to show that the funerary cult during this period was developed by an important number of people that were able to hold a wide variety of titles. Among those, there is one that looms as particularly frequent: the *hm-k3*. Usually known as the *ka*-servant or *ka*-priest, this title is almost omnipresent in Old Kingdom tombs. His main function was to satisfy the necessities of his deceased lord by providing his funerary cult with all kinds of offerings. However, in order to ensure the proper functioning of the cult and its supply, they also developed functions in the management of the properties allotted to its finance. The service of the *ka* was considered by ancient Egyptians as a communitarian system composed of several members, including women also. This circumstance makes the *hmt-k3* one of the few female ritualists in the Old Kingdom. In this paper, I have aimed to shed light upon the position of the female *ka*-servants in relation to their male counterparts. By using both iconographic and textual sources, the paper aims at understanding what women's means of access to the *ka*-servant office were, what responsibilities they held and what rights they enjoyed. The most limited occurrence of the *hmt-k3* in the sources seems to reveal a preference for men above women, and an assistance role for the latter. Despite this situation, we also find evidence of females reaching powerful positions inside the hierarchical structure of the *ka*-service, consequently one can suggest that, once inside the institution, women had similar rights to those of men.

KEYWORDS

ka-servant – funerary cult – female priest – priesthood – Old Kingdom

بعض الملاحظات على خادمة كا خلال الدولة القديمة

راؤول سانثيز كاسادو

ملخص

يبدو أن المناظر المصورة على جدران مقابر الدولة القديمة تُظهر أن الطقوس الجنائزية خلال تلك الفترة قد تم تطويرها بواسطة عدد من الأشخاص المهمين الذين حملوا مجموعة واسعة ومتنوعة من الألقاب. من بين تلك الألقاب يلوح في الأفق لقب بشكل خاص، وهو لقب *hm-k3*، والذي يُعرف عادةً بـ خادم أو كاهن الكا، وهو موجود تقريباً بجميع مقابر الدولة القديمة. كانت وظيفة حامل هذا اللقب الرئيسية هي تلبية احتياجات سيده المتوفى من خلال تقديم جميع أنواع القرابين المتعلقة بالطقوس الجنائزية. وعلى الرغم من ذلك، ومن أجل ضمان استمرار تلك الطقوس وقرابينها، تم أيضاً تطوير بعض الوظائف الأخرى في إدارة الممتلكات المخصصة لتمويل تلك القرابين. حيث اعتبر المصريين القدماء خدمة الكا نظاماً اجتماعياً يتألف من عدة أعضاء، بما فيهم النساء أيضاً. وهكذا يجعل هذا الأمر *hmt-k3* واحدة من الوظائف الدينية القليلة التي عملت بها النساء في الدولة القديمة. في هذه البحث استهدف إلى تسليط الضوء على وضع حاملات هذا اللقب من النساء ومقارنتهن بنظرائهن من الرجال. ومن خلال الاعتماد على كل من المصادر المصورة والنصية، يهدف البحث إلى فهم وسائل النساء في الوصول إلى وظيفة خادمة الكا ومسؤولياتهن والحقوق التي تمتعن بها. ومن خلال المصادر المتعددة نكتشف أن العدد القليل لنساء حملن لقب *hmt-k3* أساسه هو تفضيل الرجال عن النساء في تلك الوظيفة، حيث عملت النساء كمساعدات للرجال. على الرغم من هذا الوضع نجد أيضاً دليلاً على وصول النساء إلى مناصب قوية داخل الهيكل الهرمي لخدمة الكا، وبالتالي يمكننا اقتراح بأنه بمجرد دخول النساء للعمل في تلك الوظيفة يتمتعن على الفور بحقوق مماثلة لحقوق الرجال.

الكلمات الدالة

خادم الكا – الطقوس الجنائزية – كاهنة – كهنوت – الدولة القديمة

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